

Development and Validation of Verbal Behaviour Checklist for Children with Speech Impairment in Nigeria

By

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to develop and validate a verbal behaviour checklist for children with speech impairment. The scale is a 1-item scale that measures speech response assessed by experienced behaviourists. The scale was validated using 30 participants with varied forms of speech impairments in Abuja metropolis. The scale has a response pattern of 1- 4. The result of the analysis revealed a high intra-class reliability coefficient of .96 while factor analysis indicated a validity coefficient of .92. The raters' agreement on the participants' responses on the scale was also as high as 86.7% which indicates high agreement. This checklist is expected to be widely used in Nigeria where it is developed and validated for the measurement of speech responses among children (2-9years) with speech impairment.

Keywords: Verbal Behaviour, Speech Impairment, Checklist Development, Validation Study

Introduction

Speech response has been a perennial difficulty among children with verbal impairment for centuries. Speech impairment is an ubiquitous phenomena that occurs across continents affecting children from diverse background and ages groups. In general, speech response is the act of listening and consciously repeating someone's vocal sounds or spoken words. It is the ability to echo someone's verbal expressions as a means of learning to produce phonetic sounds or words heard from the person accurately. Skinner was the first behaviourist to coin such verbal operants as "echoic" (Skinner, 1957). Speech response is one of the basic skills of learning and acquiring speech production in a spoken language. A recent author, Cooper, et al. (2014) explained this behaviour as "word-to-word" response (stimulus – response) where an individual responds to another individual's vocal sounds/words by repeating what the speaker verbalizes. As such, it is "speech" that is the stimulus and the same "speech" from the listener, that is the response. The continuous repetition of a speaker's verbal utterance reinforces the listener by building in him, the verbal skills of the speaker. This induces him to produce a targeted phonetic sound or words like the speaker.

Speech responses (otherwise called "echoic"), talt (labelling of things), mand (making of request) and intraverbal (answering questions) are basic elements in learning of spoken language introduced by Skinner (1957) in his verbal behaviour theory (Miltenberger, 2016). Among these elementary functional language learning skills, speech response tends to be most effective in practical application in case of children suffering from speech impairment as primary diagnosis or as a symptom common in children with neurodevelopment conditions.

In some cases of abnormal verbal development, speech response (echoic) tends to play a key role in acquisition of mand, talt and intraverbal response (Kodak & Clement, 2009). When growing up, such children experience deficit in speech sound production and verbal language. This defect can be assessed, diagnosed and managed in a speech/language therapy. In the course of therapeutic intervention with children that meet up this diagnosis, there tend to be an overlap between techniques of speech language pathology (SLP) and Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) (Frosh & Bondy, 2006). Many techniques from both facets are employed in the intervention for verbal abnormalities. These techniques include Vocal Imitation Training (VIT), Stimulus-Stimulus Pairing (SSP) Dance and singing Imitation and Blow-sounding among others which are rooted in the principle of speech response. These techniques have been proven to be effective in speech therapy for children with neurodevelopmental disorders, with associative characteristics symptoms of difficulty in production and repetition of speech sounds and words (Lovaas, 2003; Cividini-Motta, et al., 2016).

Apart from the above, speech response plays important roles in evaluating client's skills in making demand, asking question, answering questions and mastering other verbal behaviours. This is most especially for children with speech impairment (Williams et al., 2000). A child may be stimulated to make demand by asking "what do you want?" Then, he/she will be given a verbal response "apple" to echo as a response to what he or she want to demand. This repeated and gradual drill to mention what he or she wants could cause the client to acquire the correct word for his demand. Then after a period of time, he/she could be able to make a demand when he/she sees apple, by mentioning "apple" as his means of making request for the fruit. This is common with children diagnosed of a neurodevelopmental condition with associative symptom of difficulty in talking.

By the same speech response mechanism, a client may be stimulated to label an object by asking a question. When asked “What is this?” A label to an object then is supplied; “ball”. The client will then label by repetition of the word “ball”. These daily speech therapy drills followed by reinforcement enhances the gradual recovery of children from symptoms of difficulty in labeling or naming objects. However, some children may still find it difficult to pronounce some words correctly, and as such may avoid the use of such words in their communication. Although, by means of repetitive drills to pronounced such words during multiple therapy sessions, they will tend to acquire the accurate pronunciation of such words.

In general, children learn to talk, recite, sing and learn by means of consistent repetition of sounds and words presented to them. In the nursery school level, much time is spent repeating teachers’ presentation of words and reading passages. Likewise, in the lower level of primary school, the school age pupils repeat phonetic sounds of various forms and attempt difficult words after their teachers’ presentation, as a way of learning and acquiring skills to articulate targeted sounds and pronounce words correctly (Schwed & Lew-Williams, 2017; Sabbar & Badr, 2015).

The religious education of children is not excluded from the presentation of words to be repeated by children. Christian children recite verses of the Bible presented by their teachers verbally (CEF, 2019). Muslim children also are taught to repeat verses presented verbatim by their teachers. This mouth to mouth, word to word repetition leads to two major achievements. First, it helps children in the acquisition of skills to pronounce words and increase their vocabulary. Secondly, word to word repetitions enhance memorization of words and reading skills in children.

Many theorists have attempted to explain how children develop verbal behaviours including speech response. Common among these theories are the Verbal behaviour theory (B.F. Skinner), Nativity theory of language acquisition (Noam Chomsky) and Cognitive theory (Jean Piaget) among many other theories. For the purpose of this study, two of these theories mentioned are briefly reviewed.

Nativity Theory of Language Acquisition: This theory (Chomsky, 1959) offers a biologically based explanation of how words and language are acquired. It is also referred to as the universal grammar theory. The theory asserts that humans are born with language acquisition devices (LAD) which unfolds naturally as an individual developed physically from infancy throughout childhood. The theorist held firm that, children do not learn language but have an innate programming of forms of language in which they follow to convey information to listeners. As they grow, they repeat phonetic sounds/words heard from others around them. They use the acquired sound/ words to fill up language form such as nouns, verbs, adjectives, preposition, phrases, sentences, figures of speech etc (Barman, 2012).

According to this theory, when their pronunciations lack criterion, the adult would correct them and ask them to repeat after them. This correction may involve presenting words and sentences for them to listen and repeat. This repeated process followed by reinforcement leads to improvement in verbal skills acquired by children as they grow. Since they are born with language acquisition programme, as they acquire words via repetition of words, those words fit into the already innate existing universal grammar structure. However, Chomsky did not point out where language acquisition device is located anatomically. Instead, he viewed language acquisition device as a psychical entity.

This theory points out the importance of repetition of words heard from others by infants and children. It also acknowledges that children that experience neurological deformity in their early years may lack in language acquisition skills. Noam Chomsky's explanation of language acquisition process also point out the relevance of speech-to-speech response in the early years of child development. In as much as children listen to adults and speak out their minds, in some situations, they need to repeat some phonetic sounds, words and phrases in order to meet up societal criterion for verbal communication and be conformed to societal norm in use of language within the family and other social gatherings. However, despite the strengths of the nativity theory, there are other theories that also explain the development of verbal behaviour.

Verbal Behaviour Theory: Skinner's (1957) verbal behaviour theory offers an opposing view to Chomsky's (1959) Universal Grammar theory. The theory traces all aspects of verbal behaviours as product of learning like any other operant behaviour. The learning process involves Stimulus-Response-Reinforcement connection. According to skinner, new born listens to the people around them and try to communicate by means of "Mand" (making request), "Talt" (labeling or naming things), "Echoic" (repetition of sounds/words), and "Intraverbal" (use of words to answer questions). According to the verbal behaviour theory, emission of phonetic sounds/words here is as a response to stimulus (i.e. need and attention) in order to be reinforced (Cooper et al., 2014; Miltenberger, 2016). For instance, if an adult holds an apple and pronounces "apple" in the presence of a child within the age of speech sound development, then the child repeats after him, and gets the apple as reinforcement. When next, the child will be more likely to repeat, because he/she had been stimulated and their response was followed by reinforcement. The consistence of this Speech-Response followed by reinforcement can lead a child that did not acquire such word or correct form of such to acquire the word to the standard set by a child's social environment. This theoretical view is applied in treatment of clients with speech impairment. Even though, this study focuses only on children with speech impairment especially those with characteristic difficulty in repetition of phonetic sounds/words. Speech response skills are applied across both regular and special need children in learning spoken languages.

Speech response skills are crucial in therapeutic interventions for children with speech impairment and learning disorders. Thus, it is important to develop a tool to assess it precisely. This study therefore, focuses on developing a reliable, valid and objective Verbal Behaviour Checklist (VBC); a tool to assess speech response of children with difficulty in repetition of sounds/words prior to therapeutic intervention and at different intervals of the intervention. This may be in the course of speech therapy session and/or during evaluation of clients' speech response skills and other related verbal operants.

Method

Population

The total number of children with speech impairment in Abuja metropolis is not known. This is because this population is scarce and there is no specific unit that record all cases of speech impairment in the metropolis. Therefore, sample of 30 children with speech impairment were used for the study.

Sampling Technique

Therefore, the researcher used convenient-census sample where all the children with speech impairment in two therapy centres within the reach of the researcher were used. The

inclusion criteria were all clients within 2-9 years, with diagnosis of neurodevelopmental disorders with characteristic symptoms of difficulty in repetition of phonetic sounds/words.

Participants

The participants for this study were 30 children with related disorders of verbal behaviours. They comprised of 20 (66.7%) males and 10 (33.3%) females. Their ages ranged from 2-9 years with a mean age of 5.557 years ($SD=2.01$). In terms of their ethnic groups, 4 (13.3%) were Hausa, 4 (13.3%) were Igbo, 4 (13.3%) were Yoruba, 2 (6.7%) were Tiv, 1 (3.3%) were Igede, 1 (3.3%) were Nupe, 1 (3.3%) were Yala, 1 (3.3%) were Tarock, 1 (3.3%) were Soko, 2 (6.7%) were Edo, 1 (3.3%) were Ibibio, 1 (3.3%) were Jukun, 2 (6.7%) were Igala, 2 (6.7%) were Fulani, 1 (3.3%) were Gbagy, 1 (3.3%) were Birom while 1 (3.3%) were Idoma. As for their religion, 19 (63.3%) were Christians while 11 (36.7%) were Muslims. Considering their primary diagnosis, 7 (23.3%) had ADHD, 9 (30%) had ASD, 3 (10%) had OND, 7 (23.3%) had IDD while 4 (13.3%) had SSD. As for their school experiences, all the participants 30 (100%) had school experience. As for the level of agreement among the raters, there was 4 (13.3%) disagreement on the ratings and 26 (86.7%) agreement on the rating.

Measure

The Verbal Behavior Checklist (VBC) is 4-point rating scale of verbal repetition of all forms of verbal expressions presented to a participant to repeat. The presenting verbal stimulus can be vowel sound, consonant sound, 1-syllable word, and 2-syllable word. The range of scores is from 1 to 4 points. In the scale, a verbal stimulus is presented once at a time in repetitive manner, till a client gets to acquire it before shifting to another one. This verbal stimulus is arranged from the simplest to the most complex. As such each participant's targeted verbal stimulus, is based on his/her previous level. In terms of scoring, a score of 1 means "passive effort", 2 means "mild effort", 3 means "moderate effort" and 4 means "good effort".

Procedure

This study was conducted among children with speech impairment in Abuja metropolis. Permission was obtained by the researcher from the administrators of 2 special need centers in Abuja for the purpose of the study. The purpose of the study was explained to the administrators of the two special needs children center, as a process of developing an instrument that could be used in the assessment of speech response of children with characteristic symptoms of difficulty in speech response. It was also explained that in the process of the study, the children will be presented with phonetic sounds and words verbally to repeat within set time by the research assistants individually. Their speech response and verbal presentation by research assistant will be recorded both on paper and an audio recorder. Behavioural therapists with two or more years of experience in working with children with neurodevelopmental disorders who volunteered for the study were trained on presenting of sound/word within 5 minutes and recording using Verbal Behavior Checklist (VBC) and audio recorder (techno T402). In each of the study unit, the participant is caused to playfully interact with research assistants using building blocks. When they get to be moderately active, targeted sound/word was presented verbally for the participant to repeat within 5 minutes. Each research assistant presented each targeted sound/word 20 times. The last response of participant was recorded by pen at the end of 5 minutes period. Within the 5 minutes period, audio recorders had been on, recording both the research assistant presentation and participant's response. At the end of the 5 minutes, the therapy sessions ends and other scheduled activities with the client is continued. The study was done in a quiet and

well-ventilated therapy room free of echo. At the end of the study, two different raters listen to the audio recorder for each study unit rated the speech response of each individual participant.

Result

The results of the analyses are presented in the tables depicted below.

Reliability and Factor Analysis

The author obtained an Intra-class Correlation Coefficient of .96 which indicates that the scale is highly reliable. It implies that the scale is consistent in measuring speech response verbal behaviour across multiple raters.

Table 1: Intra-Class reliability analysis showing the reliability coefficient obtained from the two raters' scores.

Measure	Intra-Class Correlation	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Sig
Single Measure	.914	.829	.958	.000
Average Measure	.955	.906	.978	.000

The author also obtained a correlation between the two raters in a factor analysis which yielded a correlation coefficient of .92 although with no identified factors.

Table 2: Frequency table showing the rate of agreement and disagreement of raters on the scores of participants on the Verbal Behaviour Checklist.

Rating	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	4	13.3%
Agree	26	86.7%
Total	30	100%

The result as displayed in table 2 shows that the raters disagreed on 4 (13.3%) of the speech responses produced by the participants while they agreed on 26 (86.7%). This means that the scale is measuring speech response in a valid and consistent manner as indicated by the agreement rate of the raters.

Discussion

The objective of this study was to develop verbal behaviour checklist (VBC) as a reliable, valid and objective scale use in assessment of speech response among special need children diagnosed with condition of neurodevelopmental disorder with associative symptom of difficulty in repetition and/or production of vocal sounds/words. The result of two inter-raters shows intra-class correlation coefficient that is very high which implies that the scale is highly reliable and objective. Correlation between two raters in a factor analysis also yielded higher correlation coefficient as an indication that the instrument is highly valid in the measurement of speech response.

Conclusion

It is imperative to infer at this point that the Verbal Behaviour Checklist herein developed and validated has produced promising results since the scale has demonstrated high levels of validity and reliability. Even, though the sample used for the validation was small, the scale will be widely used within Nigeria for the assessment of verbal behaviours specifically speech response.

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